

ELIXIR

Handbook of Operations

February 2018

ELIXIR Handbook of Operations

1. Purpose	3
2. Governance and groups	3
ELIXIR Consortium Agreement	3
ELIXIR Collaboration Agreement	3
Policies	3
Governance structure	3
Operational structure and responsibilities	4
ELIXIR Hub	5
3. Nodes and Service provision	5
The scope and terms of ELIXIR Services	5
Establishing a Node	5
Service Delivery Plans	5
Node review	5
ELSI Policy	5
Letters of support from the Hub	6
Process for selecting Node participation in ELIXIR's External Grant applications	6
Core Data Resources	6
Deposition Databases	6
4. ELIXIR Programme	6
The ELIXIR annual cycle	7
Commissioned Services	7
Implementation Studies	7
Guidelines for administrative aspects of Implementation Studies	7
Infrastructure Services	8
Staff Exchange Programme	8
5. Project Management Unit	8
Project Management Unit activities	8
Funding opportunities and proposal preparation	8
Guidance on project implementation and reporting	8
Linked Third Parties	9
Project dissemination	9
Other Project Management Unit resources in preparation	9
6. Communications and External Relations	9
Communications Strategy	9
Node Toolkit	10
Intranet	10

ELIXIR Channel on F1000R	10
Industry Strategy	10
International Strategy	10
7. Technical Operations	10
FAIR data management in life sciences	11
Indicators for Core Data Resources	11
Collaboration Strategy with GA4GH	11
Bioschemas	11
ELIXIR AAI	11
Use of the ELIXIR Git repository	11
Open Source Software Principles	11
Interoperability Knowledge Hub	12
References	12

1. Purpose

The ELIXIR Handbook of Operations is the main source of information on ELIXIR procedures, recommendations and guidelines. A new version is released annually as part of the EXCELERATE project. The handbook is aimed for the whole ELIXIR community, including all staff in ELIXIR Nodes, ELIXIR Hub staff, ELIXIR Board members and national funders.

The handbook is available on the ELIXIR Intranet and as the material evolves, it will be deeply integrated with the ELIXIR website and intranet.

2. Governance and groups

This section provides information on the ELIXIR Governance structure and the legal framework under which we operate. It provides a description of the roles of the Governance bodies and responsibilities of ELIXIR's operational groups (including terms and Rules of Procedure of the groups). The section also describes ELIXIR-wide Policies, as approved by the ELIXIR Board.

ELIXIR Consortium Agreement

[ELIXIR Consortium Agreement](#) (ECA) is the legal basis for ELIXIR. It establishes an organizational structure and defines the relationship between the ELIXIR Hub and the ELIXIR Nodes, specifies the EMBL's role as host of ELIXIR and sets out the ELIXIR Members' rights and obligations.

A [FAQ on the legal framework of ELIXIR](#) provides answers and explanations to the frequently asked questions about the legal framework of ELIXIR.

[Up-to-date information on ELIXIR Member States](#) is available on the ELIXIR website.

ELIXIR Collaboration Agreement

The [ELIXIR Collaboration Agreement](#) is the legal document that ties together the ELIXIR Hub with the national Node.

Policies

Via the Collaboration Agreement, the ELIXIR Nodes have to follow ELIXIR Policies approved by the ELIXIR Board.

[Categories and approval levels of ELIXIR-wide policies and guidelines](#)

ELSI POLICY

EP1 - ELIXIR [ELSI Policy](#)

Governance structure

The [ELIXIR Governance structure](#) is defined in the ELIXIR Consortium Agreement.

The [ELIXIR Board](#) appoints and dismisses the [ELIXIR Director](#) who is responsible for executing board decisions. The ELIXIR Board also appoints the members of the [ELIXIR Scientific Advisory Board \(SAB\)](#), which advises the ELIXIR Board and the ELIXIR Director in scientific and ELSI

matters. Furthermore, the [Heads of Nodes Committee](#), comprising representatives of the ELIXIR Nodes and EMBL-EBI, gives advice to the ELIXIR Board and Director in relation to ELIXIR activities.

In addition to these committees, the ELIXIR Board may establish additional advisory bodies and form working groups where this is necessary for the proper functioning and achievement of ELIXIR's goals, e.g. an [Industry Advisory Committee](#).

Principles of meeting procedures for ELIXIR groups

Each permanent group of ELIXIR has agreed on their principles for meeting procedures. The links to these documents are provided below.

Group	Terms of Reference	Rules of Procedure
Board	Defined in the ECA	Pdf
Heads of Nodes Committee	Defined in the ECA	Pdf
Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)	Pdf (Approved by ELIXIR Board)	Pdf
Industry Advisory Committee (IAC)	Pdf (Approved by ELIXIR Board)	Pdf

Operational structure and responsibilities

The [operational structure](#) of ELIXIR consists of service Platforms and scientific Use Cases.

ELIXIR has five operational platforms: Data, Tools, Compute, Interoperability and Training. Each platform is led by a leadership team - Platform Leads and Executive Committee - agreed by the Heads of Nodes Committee. The Platform membership consists of task leads, technical contributors, and a Platform Coordinator based at the ELIXIR Hub. Each Platform Coordinator provides support to the Platform leaders and ensures that the Platform's activities are aligned to its goals.

ELIXIR currently has four scientific Use Cases funded through the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project: Marine Metagenomics, Plants, Rare Disease and Human Data. In addition, three new Use Cases were selected in 2017: Proteomics, Metabolomics and Galaxy.

Node Coordinator groups

The [Technical Coordinators Group \(TeCG\)](#) is a group comprised of technical ELIXIR Node representatives. It identifies gaps and promotes connections among Nodes and platforms. It is the responsibility of the TeCG to explore technical opportunities and issues aiming to provide advice and recommendations. The TeCG is connected with platforms through Node technical representatives actively involved in the implementation of platforms.

The [Training Coordinators Group \(TrCG\)](#) is composed of training representatives of each of the ELIXIR Nodes. TrCG meets regularly to share information, expertise and to coordinate and lead the implementation of the ELIXIR training strategy across Europe.

The [Coordinators guidelines](#) provide further detail on the role and remit of these groups. The [performance indicators for permanent working groups](#) have also been defined.

ELIXIR Hub

The [ELIXIR Hub](#) coordinates the infrastructure and accommodates executive management and administrative staff.

3. Nodes and Service provision

ELIXIR Nodes, sited throughout ELIXIR Member States, run the resources and services that are part of ELIXIR. These include: data resources; bio-compute centres; tools; services for the integration of data, software, tools and resources; training; and standards expertise. The integration of these Nodes across Europe is supported by the ELIXIR Hub.

This chapter contains reference material useful for ELIXIR Nodes, including templates for Node application and Node review, the scope and terms of ELIXIR Services and instructions for preparing Service Delivery Plans.

The scope and terms of ELIXIR Services

To clarify what the word “Service” means in the ELIXIR context, a [definition of terms and scope of ELIXIR Services](#) is provided. The document also defines the role of the ELIXIR Node with regards to ELIXIR Services and discusses the benefits and responsibilities that come with the “ELIXIR Service” label.

Establishing a Node

[Guidelines how countries join ELIXIR and establish a Node](#) are available. This requires both the government of the country and the scientific community to work together.

Service Delivery Plans

Each Node, with support from the ELIXIR Hub, will prepare a Service Delivery Plan that outlines those services that the ELIXIR Node puts forward to ELIXIR and which are funded by the Node (Node-funded Services). The Service Delivery Plan is an annex to the [Collaboration Agreement](#) concluded between the ELIXIR Hub and the Node and is approved by the ELIXIR Board.

[Guidelines for the development of Service Delivery Plans](#) are available and the Hub will work together with each Node to prepare the Service Delivery Plan.

Node review

Once established, ELIXIR Nodes are regularly reviewed by the ELIXIR Scientific Advisory Board. Each year, 3-5 Nodes are invited to submit their update via the Node review form and attend the annual SAB meeting to present an update from their Node. After the meeting, the SAB submits a review of the Node to the ELIXIR Board. [Guidelines for ELIXIR Node review](#) have been approved by the ELIXIR Board and provide further information on the review process and also include forms to be used by the Node and the SAB in the review process.

ELSI Policy

EP1 - ELIXIR [ELSI Policy](#)

Approved by the Board in November 2016.

Related documents:

- [ELSI Policy Background Document](#)

Letters of support from the Hub

The Hub is happy to provide Letters of Support to ELIXIR Nodes according to our [principles for providing Letters of Support to ELIXIR Nodes](#).

Process for selecting Node participation in ELIXIR's External Grant applications

The ELIXIR HoN have agreed an approach to be followed for [the selection of ELIXIR Node partners when applying for external grants](#) including Horizon 2020 and the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI).

Core Data Resources

The ELIXIR Core Data Resources are defined as a set of European data resources that are of fundamental importance to the broad life science community and the long-term preservation of biological data. The process for selecting ELIXIR Core Data Resources has been developed by the Data Platform and was published on ELIXIR's F1000Research channel (Link to article: [Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources](#)). The [details of the first selection round are available](#).

[The initial list of Core Data Resources was published 25 July 2017.](#)

The second round of Core Data Resource selection opened in December 2017 and is expected to be concluded in the summer 2018.

Deposition Databases

In addition to the list of Core Data Resources, ELIXIR has compiled a list of [databases that it recommends for the deposition of experimental data](#). The purpose of this list is to provide guidance to journals and funders on the appropriate repositories in which to publish open data in the life sciences. [The process to select Deposition Databases](#) has been approved by the ELIXIR HoN.

4. ELIXIR Programme

The [ELIXIR Programme](#) is the five-year scientific plan of ELIXIR, prepared by the ELIXIR Director in consultation with the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes Committee and adopted by the ELIXIR Board to fulfil the purpose and goals of ELIXIR. The current Programme spans years 2014-2018. It is accompanied by the [ELIXIR Financial Plan](#) that sets out the indicative budget and membership fees in ELIXIR over the same period. ELIXIR is currently developing the next quinquennial Programme and details of this process are available on [the ELIXIR 2019-23 Programme webpage](#).

The ELIXIR annual cycle

Within the framework of the five-year scientific Programme, each year the annual ELIXIR Work Plan and Budget are prepared by the ELIXIR Director and approved by the ELIXIR Board. The annual Work Plan includes objectives for each ELIXIR Platform and Use Case and defines the Hub-funded activities, Commissioned Services, to be conducted each year.

The annual Work Plan and the accompanying budget are developed in an agreement with the Heads of Nodes Committee and submitted to the ELIXIR Board no later than 1 October each year.

Commissioned Services

Commissioned Services are services that generally fall under the responsibility of the ELIXIR Hub but are carried out by the ELIXIR Nodes (including EMBL-EBI) and are funded through the ELIXIR Budget. Commissioned Services are divided in two categories, short-term Implementation Studies and long-term Infrastructure Services.

The ELIXIR founding documents¹ define Commissioned Services and there are two ELIXIR Board approved documents that set out the overall process for the selection, approval and pre-financing of Commissioned Services.

[ELIXIR/2015/27.1](#) - Proposal for a process for the selection and approval of ELIXIR Commissioned Services

[ELIXIR/2016/12](#) - Guidelines for pre-financing of Commissioned Services - Implementation Studies

Implementation Studies

The [memo on ELIXIR Implementation Studies](#) provides further information on these activities funded through ELIXIR Budget.

To connect the Implementation Studies more deeply with the ELIXIR Platforms, the Hub will no longer accept unsolicited Implementation Study proposals from Nodes. From July 2016 onwards, new Implementation Studies will be proposed in two ways:

1. Specific technical projects put forward by the Platforms in agreement with the Hub
2. Submitted in response to a defined Service Request prepared by the Hub together with the Heads of Nodes.

Both processes are being developed by the Heads of Nodes Working Group on "Platform Governance, including preparing annual Work Plans and the selection of Implementation Studies".

Guidelines for administrative aspects of Implementation Studies

Once an Implementation Study has been approved as part of the ELIXIR annual Work Plan, the project can be developed. [Guidelines for setup, execution & conclusion of Implementation Studies](#) provide practical instructions for the administrative aspects.

¹ [ELIXIR Consortium Agreement](#) and [Collaboration Agreement](#)

Infrastructure Services

Processes for the selection, setup and execution of Infrastructure Services are in preparation.

Staff Exchange Programme

The purpose of ELIXIR Staff Exchange Programme is to support the exchange of staff between ELIXIR Nodes for short periods of time. This will help to strengthen the links between ELIXIR Nodes, facilitate capacity building across the infrastructure, and support the interoperability and sustainability of ELIXIR services and data resources.

The [first call for Staff Exchange projects](#) was run in summer 2017. The projects were reviewed anonymously by the ELIXIR Technical and Training Coordinators and the capacity building WP leads. 8 projects were selected for initiation in late 2017.

5. Project Management Unit

The ELIXIR Hub manages a portfolio of externally funded projects that involve ELIXIR Node Services and partners, often through large research infrastructure consortia. The Project Management Unit (PMU) supports ELIXIR with the progression of funding opportunities and assists ELIXIR Nodes and partners in the development of project consortia in line with ELIXIR strategic goals.

Project Management Unit activities

The PMU is responsible for all project management aspects of Hub-coordinated projects (including reporting, monitoring, internal communication in the project, organisation of project management meetings). It maintains an updated risk register for ELIXIR with associated mitigation plans that includes key risks from ELIXIR coordinated projects.

Funding opportunities and proposal preparation

The PMU supports ELIXIR partners with the development of new grant applications. For proposals lead by the Hub this includes project management, budget development, consolidation of partner budgets, development /consolidation of milestones and deliverables, proposal editing, and assistance with other formal requirements such as ethics. For proposals submitted by Nodes: general assistance, including advice on strategy, provision of templates, etc.

- EC Funding and Proposal Preparation
 - [Finding a call](#)
 - [Register in the EC portal](#)
 - [EC Proposal Submission Guidance](#)
 - [From evaluation to EC grant signature](#)

Guidance on project implementation and reporting

The PMU provides expertise and supports Nodes with formal aspects of project implementation (e.g. funding rules, administrative processes, workshop costs, Grant Agreement amendments etc.). It also provides project management support to Hub platform coordinators.

- [EC Grant Management](#)
- [INFORMATION: EC funding rules in a nutshell](#)
- [PROCESS: EC project reporting](#)
- [INFORMATION: Guidelines for workshops](#)
- [TEMPLATE Grant Agreement amendments - items and administrative info](#)

Linked Third Parties

The PMU supports Nodes using the EC Horizon 2020 Linked Third Party clause, under which ELIXIR can participate in consortia in a more unified manner or single infrastructure (as opposed to a large number of separate beneficiaries).

- [INFORMATION: Linked Third Parties in H2020 - practical aspects](#)
- [INFORMATION: Linked Third Parties in H2020 - ELIXIR principles](#)

Project dissemination

Externally funded activities usually have specific dissemination requirements. It is essential that funders and other stakeholders see the return on investments made into ELIXIR. To support this, together with External Relations, the PMU supports dissemination of projects output.

- See [ELIXIR Communications Strategy](#)

Other Project Management Unit resources in preparation

- INFORMATION: EC funding opportunities
- PROCESS: ELIXIR risk management
- PROCESS: Proposals writing planning

6. Communications and External Relations

This chapter contains background and links to ELIXIR's strategies concerning External Relations, particularly communications. The aim of the various documents and guides is to ensure a harmonised communications presence for ELIXIR and enable Nodes, through collaborative editing of the website, to ensure their news, content and events are captured effectively.

Communications Strategy

ELIXIR's Communications strategy provides a reference for all aspects of ELIXIR communications. The document is intended for members of ELIXIR who need a comprehensive overview of ELIXIR communications channels and policies.

- [ELIXIR Communications Strategy](#)

The [Communications Strategy review](#) conducted in 2017 presents qualitative and quantitative data to measure the effectiveness of ELIXIR Communications and provides a series of recommendations for specific communications channels and/or audience.

Node Toolkit

The [Node Toolkit provides tips and resources to help Nodes communicate efficiently](#) even without a dedicated communications officer or team. It also points out ways that Nodes could take more advantage of Hub communications for promoting activities.

Intranet

The [ELIXIR Intranet](#) allows members of the ELIXIR community to share information. It is a reference point for important documents, events and tasks. The documents below provide comprehensive guidelines on how to use the intranet:

- [Intranet guidelines](#) - Basic information about the structure and functionalities of the ELIXIR intranet.
- [Instructions for group managers](#) - Instructions how to how to view, add, invite and delete members of intranet groups, using the PERUN platform.
- [Instructions for Intranet champions](#) - Detailed instructions how to create and maintain content on the ELIXIR intranet.

ELIXIR Channel on F1000R

ELIXIR has established [an F1000R channel](#) for scientific and technical output. The [ELIXIR Publication principles](#) provide guidelines on how to publish here.

Industry Strategy

[ELIXIR's Industry Strategy](#) sets out the objectives and activities that will be carried out by partners to ensure maximum use and uptake of ELIXIR's services by industry. The Industry Strategy is reviewed periodically by the [ELIXIR Industry Advisory Committee](#).

- [Mapping of Clusters and SME Associations of relevance to ELIXIR](#)

In order to support Europe's industry and in particular its SMEs, ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme is a series of specialised events for companies, hosted by ELIXIR Nodes and funded through the ELIXIR Hub. Each Forum provides companies with the opportunity to learn more about the emerging ELIXIR services and to forge strong links with the local ELIXIR Node representatives running these services.

- [Guidelines to Organize a SME event](#)

International Strategy

[ELIXIR's International Strategy](#) sets out the priorities and activities that ELIXIR will undertake with specific countries outside Europe and relevant global, scientific initiatives.

7. Technical Operations

This section contains information and guidelines for ELIXIR's technical operations, including ELIXIR Services, guidelines developed by the community and practical information on operations.

FAIR data management in life sciences

ELIXIR has published a statement how its infrastructure will help researchers to make published life-science data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

- [ELIXIR position paper on FAIR Data Management in the life sciences](#)

This statement also voices ELIXIR's commitment to enabling the availability of FAIR data within the framework of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), an initiative of the European Commission and Member States to connect big data across Europe.

Indicators for Core Data Resources

Link to article: [Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources](#)

Collaboration Strategy with GA4GH

ELIXIR and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) have agreed on [a strategy to guide their collaboration](#) in developing and promoting standards and frameworks for the responsible sharing and reuse of genomics data.

Bioschemas

[Bioschemas](#) is an open community supported by ELIXIR to improve the discoverability of biological information and help researchers to easily find data, tools, training materials and other information they need for their research.

ELIXIR AAI

ELIXIR aims to provide a sustainable, user-friendly Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) to meet the evolving needs of all life scientists in Europe. To accomplish this, the [ELIXIR AAI Strategy](#) was agreed with the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes Committee in June 2016.

[ELIXIR AAI documentation](#) on the ELIXIR website provides more practical information on the service and how to connect your service to the AAI.

- [Standard Operational Procedure \(SOP\) for Registering Relying Services to ELIXIR AAI](#)

Use of the ELIXIR Git repository

The [ELIXIR Git repository](#) is recommended to be used for all code produced through ELIXIR-funded projects, e.g. the EXCELERATE or Implementation Study funding. To upload your code, simply just register or log in to Git.

Open Source Software Principles

[Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software have been published](#). You are welcome to [endorse](#) these recommendations and [join the open SoftDev4Research working group](#).

Interoperability Knowledge Hub

The Interoperability Platform is working on the development of an ELIXIR Interoperability Knowledge Hub of Services, Standards and Best Practice. The information in the Knowledge Hub will allow infrastructure and tool developers to assess current best practice and determine which interoperability services and standards to implement under specific circumstances. First version is expected to be released in 2018.

References

ELIXIR Consortium Agreement: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance#legal>
FAQ on the legal framework of ELIXIR: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/faqs>
ELIXIR Member States: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/nodes>
ELIXIR Collaboration Agreement: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/collaboration-agreement>
Categories and approval levels of ELIXIR-wide policies and guidelines: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1i1rhmHNsHOJltn6iLSf4RliGjEJbXWXV6zpMQU082dg/edit?usp=sharing>
Governance structure: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance>
ELIXIR Board Rules of Procedure: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1czdrbjRDUVpxQ0E/view?usp=sharing>
ELIXIR Heads of Nodes Committee Rules of Procedure: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B4WQQq4hwmbQYmRSMmRmRDJBWTO/view?usp=sharing>
Scientific Advisory Board Terms of Reference: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/17CJXfyu2CS-hXyAA5J3bC9XiohzjFPoc/view?usp=sharing>
Scientific Advisory Board Rules of Procedure: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VUuWb5Exl6DmluHp046B9y2gChkF39Eo/view?usp=sharing>
Industry Advisory Committee Terms of Reference: <https://drive.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1T0xISno2SkIpTEU/view?usp=sharing>
Industry Advisory Committee Rules of Procedure: <https://drive.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1eWd4NjIYSWFpOUU/view?usp=sharing>
ELIXIR Platforms and operational responsibilities: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance#operational>
Technical Coordinators Group: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/tecg>
Training Coordinators Group: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/training/how-organised>
Coordinators guidelines: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1UE5BVWhVOXB4Xzg/view?usp=sharing>
Performance indicators for permanent working groups: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1z8kVF5BGrUip5jFRDoDL4xpZNEO60QDTd342_0fvs/edit?usp=sharing
ELIXIR Hub: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/hub>
Definition of terms and scope of ELIXIR Services: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B6gLOq0cZG5HSF9rS2Q0Y1dYeFE/view?usp=sharing>
Guidelines how countries join ELIXIR and establish a Node: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/how-countries-join>
Guidelines for the development of Service Delivery Plans: https://docs.google.com/document/d/12tiehgtM11IEm6R2WhzTbhiutOgWhC3teHt0_CMVQo8/edit?usp=sharing
Guidelines for ELIXIR Node review: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1QW1CdEVYYzj0QmM/view?usp=sharing>

ELSI Policy:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1ZzctaV9YQUxPbW8/view?usp=sharing>

ELSI Policy Background Document:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1R4IYo_k-Qew4D-0Ur_1zt7Ph9YSAk5ar6-ihXlhG1Bw/edit

Principles for providing Letters of Support to ELIXIR Nodes:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0Bw_p-HKWUjHoOEO0Y281TVgzNkU/view?usp=sharing

Process for selecting Node participation in ELIXIR's External Grant applications:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1FR0WEjtZ5TopDI_TY_WAf14CMuWRrc8E/view?usp=sharing

Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources:

<https://f1000research.com/articles/5-2422/v1>

Implementing a process for the selection of Core Data Resources:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/12pzduv5vxUQ74YK9irXOZvmILD0qwuT2lgOOMn-sYGk/edit?usp=sharing>

ELIXIR Deposition Databases:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

Process to select Deposition Databases:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1YzUloNoply0hwGPYBV9axVa-rwjOZeGs/view?usp=sharing>

ELIXIR Programme:

<https://drive.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1Q1aQ01wTINzN0E/view?usp=sharing>

ELIXIR Financial Plan:

<https://drive.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/file/d/0B7btK9HAXhx1dy1ZejRXdWotMIE/view>

Development of the ELIXIR 2019-23 Programme:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/what-we-do/elixir-programme-2019-2023>

ELIXIR-2015-27.1 - Proposal for a process for the selection and approval of ELIXIR Commissioned Services:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B4WOOq4hwmbQUWd3S212Y0VxU00/view?usp=sharing>

ELIXIR/2016/12 - Guidelines for pre-financing of Commissioned Services - Implementation Studies:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B4WOOq4hwmbQWVgwZ2NEY2lkRDg/view?usp=sharing>

Memo on ELIXIR Implementation Studies:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8in1NtGRloYMmdzQlBsN3hXbVU/view?usp=sharing>

Guidelines for setup, execution & conclusion of Implementation Studies:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/12rvQQCb3bPz_t37jzIWae5UCQSFQR1jFgKz39U8zttA/edit?usp=sharing

ELIXIR Staff Exchange Programme:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B6gLOq0cZG5HMxVpay1wdkJKMDg/view?usp=sharing>

INFORMATION: EC funding rules in a nutshell:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1W4QcwwSYjKliolQcLWcpO4t1BjH-wFdRLjSEwfbaySM>

PROCESS: EC project reporting:

https://docs.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/document/d/14Nr4MBAENI9cITTsWjAy8Sx4AQAXRjwXkHv_2iFmzk8/edit?usp=sharing

Guidelines for workshops:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/guidelines-and-tips-organising-elixir-workshops>

TEMPLATE: Grant Agreement amendments - items and administrative info:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Qo4ulHs2q1gcfUMTFexAEEiigHEpf_iFPCOKnMa-GXs

INFORMATION: Linked Third Parties in H2020 - practical aspects:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1LekVEVtIFf4jBRXqAxbcDQEfqYO_96j5mXIFZTqbTpw

INFORMATION: Linked Third Parties in H2020 - ELIXIR principles:

https://docs.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/document/d/1HAq9Lnbh_Rlho-mhMkTpgXeIqHDt01zu2tssM8oSHOo/edit?usp=sharing

ELIXIR Communications Strategy:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-communications-strategy>

Communications Strategy Review:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_oljjK4pfa1lj524XiqKN1RaY_Bent5m/view?usp=sharing

Node toolkit:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/intranet/node-toolkit>

The ELIXIR intranet:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/intranet>

Intranet guidelines:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/about/intranet-guide>

Instructions for group managers:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1-YV6KeyWmNI8hTQmDvuhYSSzI6F9pUBPZpuOD2ErQDY/edit>

Instructions for Intranet champions:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Pft7EWqDhIBS-cOYjChPuz4lo1s2-1CgxWxbhKoVcA/edit#F1000R>

F1000R channel:

<http://f1000research.com/channels/elixir/>

ELIXIR Publication principles:

<https://docs.google.com/a/ebi.ac.uk/document/d/1Xffdea4iUj1mv-vYgiAoZzFAXe0b1gdHo9egrsfPjw/edit?usp=sharing>

ELIXIR's Industry Strategy:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-industry-strategy>

Mapping of Clusters and SME Associations of relevance to ELIXIR:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B8in1NtGRloYWEExHQ3UyVmFhaWc>

Guidelines to Organize a SME event:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/guidelines-organize-sme-event>

ELIXIR's International Strategy:

<https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/collaborations/international-strategy>

ELIXIR position paper on FAIR Data Management in the life sciences:

<https://f1000research.com/documents/6-1857>

Collaboration Strategy with GA4GH:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1d8ECjHwGb5q0MOEAdgyR3daH7MBIrt6b/view>

Bioschemas: <http://bioschemas.org/>

ELIXIR AAI strategy: <https://zenodo.org/record/148302#.WAjal5MrKEI>

ELIXIR AAI documentation: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aa>

Standard Operational Procedure (SOP) for Registering Relying Services to ELIXIR AAI:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1v42tacXeUYPGN0bEURdKsiRZQTC6geLhh9OYNjOL5_U/edit?usp=sharing

ELIXIR Git repository: <https://github.com/elixir-europe>

ELIXIR Open Source Software Principles: <https://f1000research.com/articles/6-876/v1>

SOftDev4Research working group: <https://github.com/SoftDev4Research/working-group>